

CEPHIA

*Consortium for the Evaluation and
Performance of HIV Incidence Assays*

Bio-Rad GS HIV-1/HIV-2 PLUS O EIA Avidity Assay

Evaluation Report

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Evaluation of Bio-Rad GS HIV-1/HIV-2 *PLUS O* EIA Avidity Assay

HIV Antibody Avidity Measurements for Distinguishing Recent HIV-1 Infections using modified Bio-Rad Genetic Systems HIV-1/HIV-2 *PLUS O* EIA

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Summary

Background

Monitoring the prevalence of HIV provides a blunt tool for understanding both recent transmission rates and the impact of behavioural changes or public health interventions on these rates. Consequently, there has been increasing application of assays, which are able to distinguish between ‘recently’ acquired HIV-1 infections and ‘long-standing’ infections, in cross-sectional surveys, to estimate HIV incidence. A comparative analysis of these existing incidence assays is a logical and necessary next step to facilitate the introduction of HIV incidence assays into wide use. In this assay, Bio-Rad GS HIV-1/HIV-2 *PLUS O* EIA Avidity Assay, we are using the test off-label and with a modified specimen procedure. The results presented here relate to the performance of the assay in a modified format and do not relate to the original U.S. FDA licensed HIV blood screening and diagnostic assay.

Evaluation Panel

The ‘evaluation panel’ consists of 2,500 uniquely-labelled HIV+ plasma specimens obtained from 928 distinct subjects, and was provided to laboratories in 5 sets of 500 specimens each. 75 of these specimens represent 25 aliquots of each of 3 underlying specimens, and acted as (unmarked) controls. Laboratory technicians were blinded to the specimen background information.

Data Analysis –

The assay characteristics, namely the mean duration of recent infection (MDRI – average time ‘recent’ while infected for less than some time T) and false-recent rate (FRR – probability of a ‘recent’ result for an individual infected for longer than T), were estimated in a number of specimen sets. The MDRI (excluding treated subjects and identified elite controllers) is 333 days (95% CI: 302-363), for $T=2$ years and a Western blot HIV diagnostic test. The FRR in this specimen set is 6% (95% CI: 4-10%). High FRRs occur amongst treated subjects (50%), elite controllers (>10%) and virally suppressed subjects (>40%).

Technical Appraisal

This assay is widely available 3rd generation, HIV-1/HIV-2 antibody only test. It requires a skilled laboratory technician and lab equipment including incubator and plate reader. Plate washer is required to control the wash quality and reduce run to run variability. It also requires a stable electrical main supply but no additional electrical works. The assay is modified and requires a 1:10 dilution of the specimen, in either wash buffer or wash buffer containing DEA during the initial incubation step. Although there is no independent EQA programme for the modified assay a set of blinded specimens is available from CDC for laboratories using the assay.

Conclusions

This does not reach the Target Product Profile (TPP) for use in cross sectional incidence assays and we do not recommend its use alone.

Background

It has become recognized that monitoring the current burden or prevalence of HIV (the fraction of the population infected at a point in time) provides a blunt tool for understanding both recent transmission rates and the impact of behavioural changes or public health interventions on these rates. Consequently, there has been increasing application of tests, which are able to distinguish between ‘recently’ acquired HIV-1 infections and ‘long-standing’ infections, in cross-sectional surveys, to estimate HIV incidence (the rate of new infections). The term Recent Infection Test Algorithm (RITA) has been coined to describe assays, or combinations of assays and other (clinical) criteria, that are able to identify ‘recent’ HIV infection. A highly sensitive HIV diagnostic test is used to identify HIV-positive subjects in the survey, and then the RITA (which could make use of any of a number of assays or biomarkers) is applied to the specimens drawn from these HIV-positive subjects. Typically, the signal of the biomarkers that are measured by the RITA gradually increase over a period of several months following primary HIV infection, and infections are classified by reference to thresholds on the biomarker readings.

It has been recognized at various meetings of the World Health Organisation (WHO) Technical Working Group on Incidence Assays that a statistically sound comparative analysis of existing incidence assays is a logical and necessary next step to facilitate the introduction of HIV incidence assays into wide use. In 2011, The Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation funded a project called *‘Development of specimen repository and evaluation of assays for identification of recent HIV infection and estimation of HIV incidence’* to help achieve this aim.

CEPHIA

The **Consortium for the Evaluation and Performance of HIV Incidence Assays** (CEPHIA) brings together world leaders in the development, performance evaluation and application of RITAs for identifying ‘recent’ HIV infection. CEPHIA’s purpose is to successfully deliver the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation funded project, to advance the understanding and performance of currently available assays, and to better describe the duration of time for which assays classify infections as ‘recently’ acquired and the rate at which they (mis)classify infections of long-infected subjects as ‘recent’.

Specific project objectives are to evaluate and compare currently available incidence assays using a common set of specimens collected for this purpose; and to assess the ability of the assays, alone or in combination, to accurately and precisely estimate HIV incidence in populations.

An overview of CEPHIA, related documentation and updates are available at <http://www.incidence-estimation.org/page/cephia-overview>

Appendix 2 details CEPHIA group members.

Introduction

As part of the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation funded project, 'Development of specimen repository and evaluation of assays for identification of recent HIV infection and estimation of HIV incidence', the CEPHIA group undertook evaluations of a number of available assays. This report details the results of the evaluation of the **Bio-Rad GS HIV-1/HIV-2 PLUS O EIA Avidity**.

A CEPHIA 'qualification panel' of specimens was used for preliminary assessment of the assay's potential for determining HIV recency, before a full assessment was undertaken using a larger 'evaluation panel' of specimens.

CDC was responsible for the test method used for the evaluation. Testing was performed by four CEPHIA approved testing sites which all completed CDC hosted training sessions in the use of the assay prior to undertaking the evaluation.

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4. JHU – John Hopkins University, Baltimore, USA

The results of this analysis are discussed in 'The performance of candidate assays to detect recent HIV infection for cross-sectional incidence estimation: an independent, comparative evaluation'. Poster 1056, *20th Conference on Retroviruses and Opportunistic Infections 2013* [2].

Full evaluation of the **Bio-Rad GS HIV-1/HIV-2 PLUS O EIA Avidity** was considered justified following review, by the CEPHIA management team, of data analysis from the Qualification Panel evaluation. The Evaluation Panel testing was performed at BSRI.

The panel of 2,500 HIV-1 positive plasma specimens used for the evaluation were sourced by the CEPHIA team at UCSF – University of California and comprised a wide range of suitable and challenging specimen types. Tables 3 - 5 summarises the specimen types used in the evaluation.

All Evaluation Panel data was analysed by the CEPHIA team at SACEMA - South African Centre for Epidemiological Modelling and Analysis, Stellenbosch, South Africa

This evaluation aims to advance the understanding and performance of currently available HIV assays, and to better describe the duration of time for which assays classify HIV infections as 'recently' acquired and the rate at which they (mis)classify infections of long-infected subjects as 'recent'. The reported analysis focuses on estimation of the characteristics of this HIV incidence assay, namely the mean duration of recent infection (average time spent 'recently' infected) and false-recent rate (proportion of long-infected subjects who are classified as 'recently' infected), for various subpopulations. Standard operating procedures for and experiences in, the laboratory application of this HIV incidence assay are also discussed.

Bio-Rad GS HIV-1/HIV-2 PLUS O EIA Avidity Protocol

Description

Description of Assay

Bio-Rad GS HIV-1/HIV-2 PLUS O EIA is an enzyme immunoassay utilising recombinant proteins and synthetic peptides for the detection of antibodies to human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (Groups M and O) and/or type 2 (HIV-1/HIV-2) in human serum or plasma and is used as an aid in the diagnosis of HIV infection. This test has been modified from its approved use to include a sample dilution of 1:10 and incubation at 4°C. During a second incubation, specimens are tested in the presence and absence of 0.1M Diethylamine (DEA) in separate wells. The difference in reactivity of the two wells allows an avidity index to be calculated which can be used to determine whether HIV is likely to have been acquired recently.

Summary and explanation of the test

After HIV infection, antibodies not only increase in concentration over time but also bind more tightly to HIV antigens. By using DEA, a chaotropic agent, the weakly-bound antibodies are dissociated allowing the less avid antibodies to be washed away, leaving only the strongly bound antibodies to be detected in the assay. The results are reported as an Avidity Index (AI) which is a ratio of the optical density (OD) reading in the DEA incubated wells to the OD reading in the diluted wash solution incubated control wells. This gives a ratio of weakly versus strongly bound antibodies/total antibodies. Recent infection should have a low AI and longstanding infection should have a high AI.

One caveat is that very low concentrations of antibody from very early infection may give a false longstanding result. CDC method states that 'determination of recent vs. long term infection cannot be made for a specimen that falls below the cutoff value of the assay with negative control with wash buffer control well'. The cutoff value is calculated by adding 0.250 OD units to the mean OD unit value calculated for the triplicate negative control with wash buffer control wells.

Principles of the procedure

The GS™ HIV-1/HIV-2 PLUS O EIA is an enzyme immunoassay based on the principle of the direct antibody sandwich technique. Microwell strip plates (the solid phase) are coated with purified antigens: gp160 and p24 recombinant proteins derived from HIV-1; a peptide representing the immunodominant region of the HIV-2 transmembrane glycoprotein, gp36; and a synthetic polypeptide mimicking an artificial (i.e., encoded by no existing virus) HIV-1 group O specific epitope. Samples and controls are added to the wells along with Specimen Diluent. The Specimen Diluent contains a dye which changes colour from purple to blue when combined with a sample or control. The wells are incubated and then washed. The next step is the addition of a coloured Conjugate Solution (green), which contains peroxidase-conjugated antigens (peptides mimicking various immunodominant epitopes of

the HIV-1 and HIV-2 transmembrane glycoproteins, and a p24 recombinant protein). The wells are then incubated. If HIV-1 and/or HIV-2 antibody is present, it will bind to the antigen coated on the well and to the peroxidase-conjugated antigens in the Conjugate. The antigen-antibody-antigen complexes remain bound to the well during the subsequent wash step, which will remove any unbound materials. Working TMB Solution is added to the plate and allowed to incubate. A blue or blue-green colour develops in proportion to the amount of HIV antibody present in the sample. Colour development is stopped by the addition of acid, which changes the blue-green colour to yellow. The optical absorbance of specimens and controls is determined spectrophotometrically at a wavelength of 450 nm (**taken from Bio-Rad GS PLUS O EIA kit package insert # 506002, revised April 2006**).

AVIDITY MODIFICATION:

The above standard assay procedure has been modified to allow an avidity index to be calculated which can be used to determine whether HIV is likely to have been recently acquired.

Test specimens and Internal Quality Controls (IQCs) are diluted 1 in 10 in COLD HIV PLUS O sample diluent and incubated at 4°C for one hour. During a second incubation, specimens are tested in the presence and absence of 0.1M Diethylamine (DEA) in separate wells. Diluted Wash Solution is used as the control for wells without DEA. DEA is a chaotropic agent which will affect weak hydrogen bonds and this will disrupt the secondary structure of proteins. HIV antibodies present in the sample will bind to the HIV antigen coated solid phase. At the lower temperatures at which this assay is performed low avidity antibody binding is decreased. Antibodies from those recently seroconverted to HIV have a lower avidity and are more susceptible to the effects of DEA than from those whose infection is longer term. This will mean that in those recently infected the DEA incubated specimen well will have less antibody-antigen binding and thus a lower OD signal will be produced than in the Diluted Wash Solution incubated control well tested at the same time. Specimens from long standing HIV infections will give a similar OD signals between the test and control wells.

A full Standard Operating Procedure for the GS HIV-1/HIV-2 PLUS O EIA assay avidity modification is available from the CEPHIA website.

Table 1: HIV Assay Information Summary

General	
Assay Name	Bio-Rad Avidity Assay(modified)
Manufacturer	Bio-Rad
Catalogue Number	32588 -480 tests 32589-960 tests 25256-4800 tests
Number of Specimens per/96 wells – Screen mode	42
Presentation	
Assay type	Recombinant and Synthetic Peptide Enzyme Immunoassay (EIA)
Antigens	Microwell plate with adsorbed purified HIV-1 and HIV-2 antigens. ProClin® 150 preservative
Specimen Diluent	Fetal calf serum Buffer with protein stabilizers 0.1% ProClin® 300 preservative Sample indicator dye
Conjugate	Purified HIV-1 and HIV-2 antigens labelled with peroxidase Buffer with protein stabilizers 0.005% Gentamicin sulfate 0.5% ProClin® 300 preservative Green dye
Conjugate Diluent	Buffer with protein stabilizers 0.1% ProClin® 300 preservative
Substrate (Chromogen)	Tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) – 11X diluted in substrate buffer
Substrate Buffer	Hydrogen peroxide Citric acid/Sodium acetate buffer DMSO
Stop Solution	1N Sulfuric acid (H ₂ SO ₄)
Reading wavelength	450 nm filter with 615 to 630 nm as reference filter
Negative Control	Human serum; negative for HIV and HCV antibodies and HBsAg 0.005% Gentamicin sulfate 0.16% ProClin® 950 preservative
HIV-1 Positive Control	Human HIV-1 antibody Non-reactive for HBsAg and antibodies to HCV 0.005% Gentamicin sulfate 0.16% ProClin® 950 preservative
HIV-2 Positive Control	Human HIV-2 antibody Non-reactive for HBsAg and antibodies to HCV 0.005% Gentamicin sulfate 0.16% ProClin® 950 preservative
HIV-1 Group O Positive Control	Rabbit HIV-1 Group O antibody diluted in Human Serum, negative for HIV and HCV antibodies and

	HBsAg 0.005% Gentamicin sulfate 0.16% ProClin® 950 preservative
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Stages	
Reagent Preparation Time	60 mins to reach room temperature
Specimen Pre-dilution set-up time	30 minutes
Sample dilution 1/Sample dilution 2/Conjugate/Substrate incubations	60 mins/30 mins/30 mins/30 mins
Total time to completion	4 hours

Equipment Required	
Bio-Rad GS HIV-1/HIV-2 PLUS O EIA	Catalogue No. 32588,32589, 25256
Diethylamine	Sigma, Catalogue No. D0806
Aspiration/wash system	Capable of dispensing and aspirating a minimum 400 µL per well
Incubators	37°C and 25°C
Microtiter plate reader	Dual wavelength capacity for 450 nm with 615 to 630nm as reference wavelength.
Pipettes	Single (10 to 100 µL), Multi-channel (50 to 300µL) plus filter tips
Graduated cylinder	50 mL or equivalent
Polypropylene Titertubes	(if samples to be pre-diluted)
Biohazardous waste containers	Do not autoclave solutions containing bleach
Appropriate PPE	Gloves, safety glasses, lab coat

In addition to the standard assay controls further controls are required for this modified HIV avidity assay. These were supplied by the Centers for Disease Control, Atlanta.

Evaluation Panel and Method

The CEPHIA evaluation panel consists of 2,500 uniquely-labelled HIV-1 positive plasma specimens obtained from 928 distinct subjects, and was provided to laboratories in 5 sets of 500 specimens each. 75 of these specimens represent 25 aliquots of each of 3 underlying specimens, and acted as (unmarked) controls. Laboratory technicians were blinded to the specimen background information.

Evaluation panel testing is intended to provide the relevant data to estimate assay characteristics, assess and compare assay performance, and optimize the algorithms of assays and biomarkers used in RITAs, for purposes of estimating HIV incidence.

Tables 2 to 6, and Figure 1, describe the sources and characteristics of specimens included in the evaluation panel.

The CEPHIA Evaluation Panel was tested using modified Bio-Rad GS HIV-1/HIV-2 PLUS O EIA for avidity testing.

Prior to beginning the evaluation, the evaluator(s) attended a training workshop provided by the assay developer (not the assay manufacturer) – U.S. Centers for Disease Control (CDC) to ensure evaluators were properly trained in the use of the modified kit and equipment.

The evaluation was conducted under the strict quality requirements as laid out in the CEPHIA Quality Management Strategy (Document 002). Refer to Appendix 1 – Evaluation Protocol for further details.

KIT LOT: 083GBB ,
CATALOG #: 25256
EXPIRY DATE: 15 NOVEMBER 2012

KIT LOT: 255GBB ,
CATALOG #: 32588
EXPIRY DATE: 15 MAY 2013 255GBB-05

STORAGE OF ASSAY KITS: Kits are stored at 4°C with a defined expiration date. The kits we used were within 1 month of the expiration date.

Equipment was provided by Bio-Rad and installed at BSRI by a Bio-Rad field service engineer. The incubator and refrigerator temperatures were monitored on the data recording sheets. There were no significant variations in the temperatures recorded.

All equipment (plate washers, pipettes, readers and incubators) had undergone appropriate proper installation, operation and performance/monitoring qualification prior to testing to minimise assay variability.

Table 2: Source of Specimens used in the Evaluation Set

Type of partner site	Site Name	Location of specimen draws
Seroconverter Cohorts		
<p><i>US and Brazil cohorts enrolled subjects diagnosed with acute HIV seroconversion.</i></p> <p><i>IAVI Protocol C enrolled subjects who seroconverted during participation in an HIV incidence cohort study.</i></p> <p><i>All cohorts followed subjects both prior to and after antiretroviral therapy.</i></p>	UCSF Options Project	San Francisco
	UCSD Acute HIV Study	San Diego
	AMPLIAR	Brazil
	IAVI Protocol C	Kenya
		Rwanda
	Uganda	
	South Africa	
	Zambia	
HIV Positive cohorts		
<p><i>SCOPE enrolls HIV positive men and women both on and off ARV treatment, actively recruits elite controllers, and follows these subjects over time.</i></p> <p><i>SFMHS enrolled both HIV negative and HIV positive men from a population-based sample in SF and followed these subjects forward over time.</i></p>	SCOPE	San Francisco
	San Francisco Men’s Health Study (SFMHS)	
Blood Banks		
<p><i>Blood banks identify repeat blood donors with a prior negative blood donation followed by a subsequent HIV positive donation.</i></p>	American Red Cross	United States
	Blood Centers of the Pacific	
	South Africa National Blood Services (SANBS)	South Africa
	Hemocentro do Sao Paulo	Brazil

Table 3: Demographic / infection characteristics of subjects contributing specimens to the evaluation panel

Subject/ specimen group	Number of subjects (% of subjects)	Number of specimens (% of specimens)
All subjects	928 (100)	2500 (100)
Gender		
Male	728 (78)	1872 (75)
Female	194 (21)	547 (22)
Country of specimen source		
USA	523 (56)	1298 (52)
Zambia	166 (18)	508 (20)
Rwanda	65 (7)	281 (11)
Uganda	62 (7)	200 (8)
Brazil	18 (2)	85 (3)
South Africa	58 (6)	64 (3)
Kenya	36 (4)	63 (3)
Age at specimen draw (years)		
<20	28 (3)	49 (2)
20-30	231 (25)	566 (23)
30-40	357 (38)	887 (35)
40-50	270 (29)	635 (25)
50-60	92 (10)	240 (10)
>60	21 (2)	45 (2)
HIV Subtype ¹		
B	525 (57)	1247 (50)
C	250 (27)	670 (27)
A1	92 (10)	290 (12)
D	42 (5)	157 (6)
Other	19 (2)	135 (5)

¹ 42% of subjects (capturing 52% of specimens) had their HIV subtypes confirmed through laboratory testing, while the remainder of HIV subtypes were based on the majority HIV subtype in country of specimen source.

Figure 1: Number of specimens drawn over time per subject, for specimens included on the evaluation panel

Table 4: Times from (estimated) HIV infection to specimen draws for ARV-naïve subjects included in the evaluation panel (for estimation of the MDRI), stratified by HIV-1 subtype¹

	All subtypes	Subtype B	Subtype C	Subtype A1	Subtype D
Subject/ specimen group	Number of subjects				
Subject has estimable infection date ²	422	104	185	83	38
<1 year duration of infection (DOI) at specimen draw	283	59	145	39	33
1-2 years DOI	224	39	105	54	19
2-3 years DOI	125	22	56	34	11
3-4 years DOI	72	15	33	19	4
4+ years DOI	41	14	19	7	0
Subject/ specimen group	Number of specimens				
Subject has estimable infection date ²	1386	344	588	263	149
<1 year duration of infection (DOI) at specimen draw	671	164	308	71	103
1-2 years DOI	346	70	146	93	27
2-3 years DOI	189	42	72	58	14
3-4 years DOI	104	28	40	29	4
4+ years DOI	66	34	20	11	0

¹ Elite controllers (defined in *Analysis of Assay Characteristics*) from SCOPE (see Table 2) are excluded as the study specifically recruited (untreated) subjects with sustained low HIV viral loads, and therefore data would otherwise be over-enriched with elite controllers.

² Infection date refers to the time of positivity of Western blot. See *Analysis of Assay Characteristics* for the approach used for estimating infection times, and for identifying subjects with estimable infected times, for this particular analysis.

Table 5: Description of specimens from ARV-naïve long-infected subjects included in the evaluation panel (for estimation of the FRR), stratified by HIV-1 subtype¹

	All subtypes	Subtype B	Subtype C	Subtype A1	Subtype D
Subject/ specimen group	Number of subjects				
Subject infected for greater than 1 year ²	456	243	121	62	21
Subject infected for greater than 2 years ²	316	190	75	37	11
Subject infected for greater than 3 years ²	224	156	42	20	4
Subject infected for greater than 4 years ²	161	137	18	6	0
Subject infected for greater than 5 years ²	111	111	0	0	0
Subject/ specimen group	Number of specimens				
Subject infected for greater than 1 year ²	1112	538	297	210	47
Subject infected for greater than 2 years ²	665	388	144	106	18
Subject infected for greater than 3 years ²	416	301	63	43	4
Subject infected for greater than 4 years ²	285	256	19	10	0
Subject infected for greater than 5 years ²	192	192	0	0	0

¹ Elite controllers (defined in *Analysis of Assay Characteristics*) from SCOPE (see Table 2) are excluded as the study specifically recruited (untreated) subjects with sustained low HIV viral loads, and therefore data would otherwise be over-enriched with elite controllers.

² Specimen drawn at least 1, 2, 3, 4 or 5 years (see row labels) after a first recorded HIV-positive diagnosis.

Table 6: Description of *challenge* specimens drawn from subjects HIV infected for greater than 2 years included in the evaluation panel (for estimation of the FRR)¹

Subject/ specimen group	All HIV-1 subtypes ²	
	Number of subjects	Number of specimens
SCOPE elite controllers ²	31	89
CD4 cell count < 200 at draw	124	214
Treated subjects ³	113	185
Treatment initiated within 6 months of infection	53	90
Treatment initiated 6-24 months after infection	17	28
Treatment initiated >24 months after infection	33	54
Viral load < 75 copies/ml	154	273

¹ 98% of subjects (or specimens) represent HIV-1 subtype B infections.

² Subjects were identified as elite controllers by SCOPE (classification rules are outlined in defined in *Analysis of Assay Characteristics*).

³ Treated for at least 3 months and without interruption.

Analysis of Assay Characteristics

The methods and results outlined below are reported in the following journal article: ‘Kassanjee R, Pilcher CD, Keating SM, Facente SN, McKinney E, Price MA, Martin JN, Little S, Hecht FM, Kallas EG, Welte A, Busch MP, Murphy G, on behalf of the *Consortium for the Evaluation and Performance of HIV Incidence Assays* (CEPHIA); Independent assessment of candidate HIV incidence assays on specimens in the CEPHIA repository [3].

Definitions of Assay Characteristics

In 1995, Brookmeyer and Quinn [4] introduced the concept of cross-sectional HIV incidence estimation: incidence can be measured from a single survey conducted a point in time using both (i) observed survey counts of HIV-negative, ‘recently’ infected and ‘non-recently’ infected subjects, and (ii) knowledge about the dynamics of the test for recent infection. However, the state of ‘recent’ infection demonstrated in their work (namely, detectability of p24 antigens in the absence of detectable HIV antibodies) occurs for only a few weeks after infection, resulting in unrealistically large surveys being required for precise incidence estimation. Subsequently, various tests, with more enduring states of ‘recent’ infection, have been proposed. However, the behaviour of currently available tests has been imperfect – due to inter-subject variability, with a substantial proportion of long-infected individuals that nevertheless return as ‘recent’ results.

As the methodology has matured, a general theoretical framework has been derived, which consistently accounts for these ‘false-recent’ results [5]. Two test characteristics that summarise test dynamics emerge as required for purposes of incidence surveillance:

- the **mean duration of recent infection (MDRI)**, Ω_T , which is the average time spent alive and ‘recently’ infected, while infected for less than some time cut-off T , and
- the **false-recent rate (FRR)**, β_T , which is the probability that an individual who is infected for longer than T will return a ‘recent’ result.

This general framework was developed by introducing a post-infection time cut-off, T , to separate ‘true-recent’ from ‘false-recent’ results. In a cross-sectional survey, the estimate of incidence would be

$$\hat{I}_T = \frac{n_R - \hat{\beta}_T n_+}{n_S \cdot (\hat{\Omega}_T - \hat{\beta}_T T)},$$

where n_+ and $n_S = n - n_+$ are the counts of HIV-positive and HIV-negative (or susceptible) subjects in the survey, n_R is the number of ‘recently’ infected subjects in the survey, and $\hat{\Omega}_T$ and $\hat{\beta}_T$ are the estimated MDRI and FRR for the test for recent infection respectively.

This analysis focuses on estimation of the MDRI and FRR. As the characteristics of incidence assays may vary across subpopulations, the characteristics are explored using various specimen sets.

Data Analysis Methods

Software. All data captured within CEPHIA are stored in a MySQL relational database. Database queries linked assay results to the background information on subjects and specimens for data analysis, which was then performed in Matlab (R2013b, the MathWorks Inc.).

Interpretation of assay results. The results were interpreted according to developer's guidelines (see standard operating procedures on the CEPHIA project website [1]). As identified in the developer's comments later a cut-off of 40% was used for recent infection but this has now been revised down to 30% by the developer.

Stratification of data. Assay characteristics were estimated using specimen sets defined by stratifying on treatment history, viral load, CD4+ T cell count, time from infection to specimen draw, and HIV subtype (which was based on country of draw, for the 48% of specimens which lack explicit laboratory subtype confirmation). The characteristics of assays in 'elite controllers' (ECs), broadly defined as subjects who maintain undetectable or very low HIV viral loads without antiretroviral therapy (ART), is of particular interest. As the SCOPE study purposefully recruited ECs, this data was analysed separately. These subjects were ART-naïve (or without ART for at least 6 months), with all off-treatment viral load measurements (HIV-1 RNA) below 200 copies/ml and at least 50% of these measurements below 75 copies/ml.

Time cut-off T . The definitions of the MDRI and FRR rely on the previously mentioned construct of a post-infection time cut-off, T . If T is chosen to be too short, this limits the possible MDRI and typically raises the FRR. If T is chosen to be too long, it becomes difficult to obtain sufficient data to analyse the test dynamics with sufficient precision over this time after infection, and the MDRI will also develop variation by time and place (properties inevitable for the FRR) rather than capture stable biological properties of the test. A cut-off of $T = 2$ years is used throughout this work. The value of T was increased from 1 year, as used in preliminary analyses [2], to 2 years in this analysis, to better capture the tails of persisting 'recent' results and thus reduce FRRs.

Definition and estimation of infection times. In practice, the notion of 'infection' implicit in the assay characteristic definitions refers to 'detectable infection' – which depends on the particular HIV diagnostic test used in the incidence study. In this analysis, 'detectable infection' was defined as the time of seroconversion on an HIV viral lysate-based Western Blot assay. Based on the methodology summarised below, infection times were estimated for 56% of subjects.

The estimation of a subject's infection time relies on both data describing the subject's testing history and knowledge of the sensitivities of the various diagnostics tests used on the subject, where sensitivity captures the probability of detecting HIV in a (truly infected) subject as a function of time since detectability on the reference diagnostic test that is to be used in the incidence study (Western Blot in this case). In general, the formal likelihood of observing a subject's testing history can be directly generated as a function of time since HIV infection (through vertical and horizontal inversion of the various diagnostic tests')

sensitivity functions). Under prior assumptions about infection times, this likelihood function can then be used to produce an inferred posterior density function for possible infection times, which can then be used in analyses. Depending on available data, various simplifications of this estimation procedure could be considered.

For this analysis, infection times were estimated for subjects with available first HIV-positive test dates, Fiebig staging [6] information for first HIV-positive tests, and, at times, last HIV-negative test dates (within 120 days of first HIV-positive dates). The likelihood function for the infection time (corresponding to the time of entering Fiebig stage 5) of a subject was then calculated using the average durations of Fiebig stages presented in Lee et al [7] (neglecting inter-subject variability, assuming independence between diagnostic results for a subject, and making some assumptions about the types of diagnostics tests used at last HIV-negative test dates). A uniform prior time for infection times was combined with the likelihood function, and the mean of the resulting posterior distribution for infection times provided a subject's estimated infection time, which was used in all subsequent analyses.

Efforts are currently being made to capture more detailed information on cohort-level diagnostic testing protocols and more complete testing histories of individual subjects, thus providing the required data to refine estimation of infection times for later analyses of assay results.

For subjects with unambiguous acute retroviral syndrome (ARS) symptoms onset dates between last HIV-negative and first HIV-positive test dates, infection was estimated to occur 17 days after ARS onset (based on the observation that the incubation period of ARS symptoms is about 14 days [8-11] and that the time from exposure to Western blot seroconversion averages 31 days [6,7]).

Estimation of MDRI. A number of methods can reasonably be used to estimate the MDRI, each with its own accuracy, precision and complexity – as explored in a separate, detailed benchmarking exercise (manuscript in preparation, by a working group operating on behalf of the HIV Modelling Consortium [12]). In this analysis, linear binomial regression, an approach found to be robust across a number of scenarios in this benchmarking project, and previously used for this purpose [13], has been applied. The model form is $g(P_R(t)) = f(t)$ where $P_R(t)$ is the probability of testing 'recent' at time t after infection, g is the chosen link function and $f(t)$ is a linear function of the model parameters, which are estimated by a maximum likelihood approach. Results from a 4-parameter model form are presented, where g is the logit link, and $f(t)$ is a cubic polynomial in t (Model A). Data points more than $1.1 \times T$ post infection were discarded before model fitting (Data Exclusion Rule I), with the aim of achieving the best fit of the model over $[0, T]$ post-infection, while avoiding diluting the data around the boundary at T . Sensitivity of results when increasing the data exclusion cut-off to $2 \times T$ (Data Exclusion Rule II) was also considered. Variation in results was explored when fitting two other model forms, namely (i) a more restrictive 2-parameter model where g is the log-log link and $f(t)$ is a linear function of $\ln(t)$ (Model B), and (ii) a flexible 7-parameter model where g is the logit link and $f(t)$ is a linear function of the natural cubic spline basis functions with interior knots occurring every 3 months after infection, between 0 and T after infection (Model C). In all cases, the MDRI, expressed mathematically as $\int_0^T P_R(t)dt$, was estimated using the fitted $P_R(t) = g^{-1}(f(t))$.

To correctly account for the structure of the data, in the absence of explicit subject-level clustering in the fitted models, bootstrapping was performed by sampling subjects (not observations) with replacement. The 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of 10 000 MDRI estimate replicates provided 95% confidence interval (CI) limits [14].

Estimation of FRR. A population-level FRR is inherently dependent on the epidemiological and demographic history of a study population, and so a set of specimens, such as in the CEPHIA repository, can only be used to estimate the FRR in well-defined subpopulations. Therefore, specimens from long-infected subjects were identified (specimens drawn at least T after the subject's first recorded HIV-positive test time – adjusted to capture Western blot positivity), and the proportion of 'recently' infected subjects estimated in each of the specimen sets described above. To capture subject-level clustering, when a subject provided more than one result to any FRR estimate, the most frequent classification was used. When a subject had equal numbers of 'recent' and 'non-recent' classifications, the subject contributed 0.5 to the count of subjects who have a majority 'recent' classification. Exact Clopper-Pearson 95% CIs [15] are provided.

Reproducibility statistics. The sample mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation of the multiple assay measurements obtained for each of the unique reproducibility specimens, as well as each of the labelled quality controls, were also calculated.

Results

The HIV incidence assay dynamics, excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers, are shown in Figures 2 to 4. The evolution of assay measurements by time since HIV infection is shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3. In Figure 4, the proportion of 'recent' results (assay measurements below the 'recent'/'non-recent' threshold) is plotted by time since infection, also stratified by HIV-1 subtype (B, C, D, and A1). The figures show that there is natural variability in biomarker maturation, leading to a significant number of subjects reaching the standard 'recent'/'non-recent' threshold more than one year after infection; and there is significant delay or failure to achieve maturation to 'non-recent' status among specimens of subtypes A1 and D.

The distribution of assay measurements for specimens drawn more than $T = 2$ years after infection is shown in Figure 5, for various specimen sets.

Figure 2: Spaghetti plot of subjects' assay measurements as a function of (estimated) time since infection (years), excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers

The figure represents 1376 data points from 418 subjects. The 'recent'/'non-recent' threshold is shown by a horizontal solid line.

Figure 3: Box-and-whisker plots of assay measurements as a function of (estimated) time since HIV infection (years), excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers

The plot indicates percentiles of measurements in 6-monthly intervals of time after infection. The central 50% and median of measurements are captured by the box and dividing line respectively, and whiskers and markers capture remaining measurements and outliers respectively. There are 40-450 data points per group. The 'recent'/'non-recent' threshold is shown by the horizontal solid line.

Figure 4: The proportion of ‘recent’ results (%) as a function of (estimated) time since HIV infection (years), excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers and stratifying by HIV subtype (B, C, D and A1)

Circles and lines show observed proportions and 95% confidence intervals respectively. Specimens are grouped into 6-monthly intervals of time since infection until 2 years, after which all specimens are grouped together. There are 25 to 665 data points per group, except for subtype D which has fewer than 20 points 1-2 years after infection.

A. All HIV-1 subtypes

B. Subtype B

C. Subtype C

D. Subtype D

E. Subtype A1

Figure 5: Empirical distribution of assay measurements for specimens drawn greater than $T = 2$ years after (estimated) infection time, by specimen set

'Recent'/'non-recent' thresholds are shown by vertical solid lines. Note that the peak of Bio-Rad GS HIV EIA Avidity results at 100% is due to a large proportion of (treated and untreated) aliquots returning the maximum possible S/C on the reader used.

A. Excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers

665 data points from 316 subjects.

C. SCOPE elite controllers

89 data points from 31 subjects.

E. Low CD4+ T cell count

CD4 cell count < 200 cells/ μ l at draw. 214 data points from 124 subjects.

B. Treated subjects

Treated for at least 3 months without interruption. 185 data points from 113 subjects.

D. Low viral load

Viral load < 75 copies/ml at draw. 273 data points from 154 subjects.

Table 7 provides estimated assay characteristics for various specimen sets. The estimated MDRI, excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers from the analysis, is 333 days (95% CI: 302-363). The result was insensitive (less than 2% change in result) to whether ARS symptoms onset dates were used to adjust estimated infection dates, a change to Data Exclusion Rule II, the use of alternative Model C, and the use of alternative Model B (with a 3% increase in the estimate when changing to Data Exclusion Rule II within Model B).

While characteristics have been estimated here on the standardized basis of a Western blot being used to identify HIV-positive subjects, other diagnostic screening tests are likely to be used in incidence studies, and the time between HIV exposure and reactivity on these tests can differ by several weeks [6,7,16]. Therefore, for application to incidence studies, the base case MDRI reported here would need to be increased or decreased – depending on the particular screening test or algorithm used in the study to classify a specimen as HIV-positive, and hence eligible for ‘recent’ infection testing.

The estimated FRRs provided in Table 7 are also plotted in Figure 6. Excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers, and analysing all remaining specimens drawn more than $T = 2$ years after infection, the measured FRR is 6.2% (95% CI: 3.8%-9.4%). When stratifying by time since infection, some persistence of ‘recent’ classifications is evident.

The FRR amongst elite controller specimens is high at 13% (95% CI: 4%-30%). The FRR amongst treated subjects is even higher, at 50% (95% CI: 40%-60%). Further stratifying treated subjects by time from infection to treatment initiation, the FRR decreases as the time to treatment initiation increases: for early treatment initiation (within 6 months of infection) the FRR is 64% (95% CI: 50%-77%), while for later treatment initiation (more than 6 months after infection) it is 31% (95% CI: 19%-45%).

The FRR for subjects with low viral loads, here defined as below 75 copies/ml, is high, at 41% (95% CI: 33%-49%). This is consistent with results above, as 92% of this specimen set is made up of specimens from the identified elite controllers and treated subjects (and 94% of specimens from SCOPE elite controllers and treated subjects have a low viral load).

The FRR amongst subjects with low CD4+ T cell counts, namely less than 200 cells/ μ l and acting as a proxy for AIDS identification, was low at 1.6% (95% CI: 0%-5%).

Table 8 lists MDRI and FRR by subtype. Small p-values for pairwise subtype differences in the MDRI or FRRs involve subtype A1 or D (typically versus other subtypes). While these initial results highlight potential subtype differences and support further exploration of this topic, a more definitive analysis (beyond the present scope) should be performed – based on a larger number of subtype D and A1 specimens and using estimation procedures specifically adapted to this stratification.

Table 7: Estimated assay characteristics (and 95% confidence intervals), for various specimen sets

Assay characteristics are estimated for $T = 2$ years and a context in which an HIV viral lysate-based Western blot assay is used to identify HIV-positive subjects in the incidence study.

	Number of subjects (number of data points)	Estimated assay characteristics (95% CI)
MDRI in days		
All specimens, excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers	400 (1032)	333 (302-363)
FRR as %		
All specimens, excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers	316 (665)	6.2 (3.8-9.4)
By time since infection (years), excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers		
(2,3]	140 (208)	12.5 (7.5-19.1)
(3,4]	77 (110)	6.5 (2.1-14.5)
(4,5]	35 (45)	8.6 (1.8-23.1)
>5	112 (193)	0.0 (0.0-2.6)
Elite controllers (identified by SCOPE cohort)	31 (89)	12.9 (3.6-29.8)
Treated subjects (no previous treatment interruption and treated for at least 3 months)	113 (185)	50.0 (40.4-59.6)
By time from infection to treatment (years)		
[0,0.5)	53 (90)	64.2 (49.8-76.9)
≥0.5	53 (88)	31.1 (19.1-45.3)
Low viral load (<75 copies/ml at draw)	154 (273)	40.6 (32.8-48.8)
Low CD4+ T cell count (<200 cells/μl at draw)	124 (214)	1.6 (0.2-5.7)

Figure 6: Estimated proportions of 'recent' results in various sets of specimens drawn from subjects infected for greater than $T=2$ years

Table 8: Estimated assay characteristics (and 95% confidence intervals), for ARV-naïve subjects and excluding SCOPE elite controllers, by subtype

Assay characteristics are estimated for $T = 2$ years and a context in which an HIV viral lysate-based Western blot assay is used to identify HIV-positive subjects in the incidence study.

	Number of subjects (number of data points)	Estimated assay characteristics (95% CI)
MDRI in days¹		
All specimens	400 (1032)	333 (302-363)
Subtype B	90 (246)	299 (233-371)
Subtype C	181 (454)	298 (262-338)
Subtype D	38 (131)	467 (354-581)
Subtype A1	80 (166)	364 (289-442)
FRR as %²		
All specimens	316 (665)	6.2 (3.8-9.4)
Subtype B	190 (388)	2.1 (0.6-5.3)
Subtype C	75 (144)	6.7 (2.2-14.9)
Subtype D	11 (18)	54.5 (23.4-83.3)
Subtype A1	37 (106)	12.2 (3.8-27.1)

¹ In a test for pairwise differences in MDRI by subtype, using a z-test, the following pairs provided p-values below 0.05: B&D, C&D. Estimated standard deviations of the MDRI estimators are used as proxies for true values, and therefore tests are anticonservative (particularly when sample sizes are small).

² In a test for pairwise differences in FRRs by subtype, using the Fisher-Boschloo test [17], the following pairs provided p-values below 0.05: A1&B, A1&D, B&D, C&D.

Lastly, Figures 7 and 8 summarise the assay measurements for the reproducibility of CEPHIA labelled control specimens included in the evaluation. 75 of the uniquely-labelled 2,500 specimens on the evaluation panel represent 25 aliquots of each of three underlying specimens. The reproducibility of measurements for these 3 'blinded' controls is described in Figure 7. Three labelled internal quality controls were also tested regularly during evaluation panel testing, for confirmation of stability of the assay. The results for these controls are summarised in Figure 8.

Figure 7: Reproducibility of *unlabelled* controls

The box-and-whisker plots (top) provide percentiles of the 25 measurements for each of the three blinded reproducibility specimens (labelled A, B and C in the figure only). The central 50% and median of measurements are captured by the box and dividing line respectively, and whiskers and markers capture remaining measurements and outliers respectively. The ‘recent’/‘non-recent’ threshold is shown by the vertical solid line. The observed reproducibility statistics (mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation) of measurements are also tabulated (bottom).

Summary of measurements				
Specimen identifier	Number of measurements	Mean (AI)	Standard deviation (AI)	Coefficient of variation (%)
A	25	5.9	1.4	23
B	25	78.2	13.8	18
C	25	100.0	0.0	0

Figure 8: Reproducibility of CEPHIA labelled controls

The box-and-whisker plots (top) provide percentiles of the 90+ measurements for each of the three labelled quality control specimens (labelled D, E and F in the figure only). The central 50% and median of measurements are captured by the box and dividing line respectively, and whiskers and markers capture remaining measurements and outliers respectively. The 'recent'/'non-recent' threshold is shown by the vertical solid line. The observed reproducibility statistics (mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation) of measurements are also tabulated (bottom).

Summary of measurements				
Specimen identifier	Number of measurements	Mean (AI)	Standard deviation (AI)	Coefficient of variation (%)
D	93	10.0	5.5	55
E	92	21.9	7.8	35
F	93	68.1	14.2	21

Conclusion/Recommendations

The following conclusions relate to the assay in its off-label modified format and do not relate to its U.S. FDA licensed blood screening and diagnostic performance:

- 1) Given its performance in relation to the Target Product Profile and to other candidate assays this assay is not recommended as a standalone assay for use in cross-sectional incidence assays.
- 2) In particular this assay is a not promising candidate assay due to its higher False Recent Rate.
- 3) However, the CEPHIA group believe that there is considerable scope for variation in cut-offs and thresholds used in this assay which along with currently described RITA algorithms (such as those including incorporating viral load, ARV treatment history, CD4 count or another assay) may improve the performance of this assay to an acceptable level for use in cross sectional incidence estimates.
- 4) This assay is a modified commercial assay and therefore serious consideration should be given by the user on how to control any manufacturing variation in this assay which may not be apparent in the assays licensed HIV blood screening and diagnostic use.
- 5) A number of groups are looking at these modified assays for a number of different purposes and alternative target product profiles are being prepared. The use of this assay for against other TPPs will be assessed when these are published.

Technical Appraisal

Manufacturer's Kit insert instructions

The kit insert is for the Bio-Rad GS HIV-1/HIV-2 *PLUS O* EIA assay and does not list the specific modifications that apply for the Bio-Rad Avidity Assay. CEPHIA has provided the SOP (Document 014A) instructions used in this evaluation (authorized by Michelle Owen-CDC) and distributed it for use to all test sites.

QUALITY CONTROL - VALIDATION OF RESULTS

Mean Negative Control absorbance value (NCx)

Determine the mean absorbance for the Negative Control by dividing the sum of the absorbance values by the number of acceptable controls. The individual absorbance values of the Negative Control must be greater than 0.000 AU and less than or equal to 0.150 AU. One Negative Control absorbance value may be discarded if it is outside this range. The NCx may be calculated from the two remaining absorbance values.

Calculation of Results:

Cutoff Value

Determine the cutoff value by adding 0.250 to the NCx as shown in the example below:

$$\text{NCx} = 0.080$$

$$\text{Cutoff Value} = 0.080 + 0.250 = 0.330$$

Standard Assay Validation

A run is valid if the following criteria are met:

- The absorbance values of the individual Negative Controls are greater than 0.000 AU and less than or equal to 0.150 AU. One Negative Control value may be discarded. If two or more Negative Controls are out of limit, the assay must be repeated.
- The absorbance value of the HIV-1 Positive Control must be greater than or equal to 0.700 AU.
- The absorbance value of the HIV-2 Positive Control must be greater than or equal to 0.700 AU.
- The absorbance value of the HIV-1 Group O Positive Control must be greater than or equal to 0.700 AU.

If any of these criteria have not been met, the assay is invalid and must be repeated. However, for the modified assay and alternative validation is required (see below)

The presence or absence of HIV Ab is determined by relating the absorbance value of the specimen to the cutoff value. Specimens with absorbance values that are < 0.000 must be repeated. Reasons for non-repeatedly reactive specimens include:

- Improper washing of microwell plates
- Cross-contamination of non-reactive specimens with HIV-1 and/or HIV-2 Ab from a high titered specimen
- Contamination of the Working TMB Solution by oxidizing agents (sodium hypochlorite, hydrogen peroxide, etc.)

- Contamination of the Stopping Solution

Developer's instructions (CDC)

Assay Results: The results are based on the percent ratio of the results of the sample incubated with DEA and the sample incubated with Diluted Wash Buffer times 100.

An avidity calculation is performed for each sample tested to give an Avidity index (AI). CEPHIA has provided a spreadsheet for formatting and calculation of results (CEPHIA DOC ID 014B_Bio-Rad Avidity Worksheet Data Template v03).

The calculations are done as follows:

AI	=	OD Chaotropic reagent (0.1M DEA) treated sample	
		OD non-treated (wash buffer sample)	x 100%

Interpretation of Assay Results

During the screening mode, the AI value for each specimen dictates whether the specimen is considered a "long-term" seroconversion or whether it must be subjected to confirmatory testing. Specifically, if the AI of a specimen is **> 50** during the screening mode, no further testing is required and the specimen is considered a long-term seroconversion.

Confirmatory Range: (Evaluation Panel testing only)

Specimens with an AI value in the range of 20-50% should be repeated in triplicate.

During Confirmatory mode, the **median of the triplicate OD values** is used to determine the final AI;

If the OD of a specimen is **≤50%**, then the specimen is considered a recent seroconversion

If the OD is **> 50%** then the specimen is considered a long-term seroconversion.

Laboratory Run Validation

1. Kit Assay Controls: If more than one HIV negative control has an OD of **> 0.150** the run is invalid.
2. Modified assay control (IQC): Must fall within ranges set by CDC at time of provision.
Typically IC < 20% and PC > 80%
3. CEPHIA Controls: Specimens shown to give a low, medium and high avidity index were included in the assay. These specimens had to give reactivity within a predetermined range for the assay to be valid.
4. Specimen OD values must be greater than the negative cutoff value of the assay with wash buffer. The negative cutoff value is calculated by adding 0.250 to the mean OD negative value calculated for the triplicate negative control wells. **Specimens which do not meet this criteria will have a Final Result of 'Invalid assay-specific antibody criteria'**

Test runs which do not meet the quality criteria are deemed invalid and were repeated at the testing laboratory. An assay failure rate of 11% was observed.

This Bio-Rad assay is very sensitive and therefore extra care must be taken when adding specimens and reagents to prevent cross-contamination within the plate. Thus, the use of filter tips is recommended. Add diluted specimens at the bottom of the well, not touching the sides. For reagent addition, try not to allow tips to touch the plate; if necessary, only the top rim of each well. To reduce non-specific binding, ensure you wash 6 times with a 30 or 40 second soak cycle as described in the kit insert. This assay is also sensitive to time at room temperature before the initial incubation. By setting up the dilutions in titre tubes, this will allow faster plating before 4°C incubation.

Equipment

Some laboratories have reported that obtaining a 25°C incubator may pose some difficulties for them.

Technical Conclusions

The Bio-Rad Avidity assay is a commercially manufactured EIA assay that has been modified for identifying recent HIV infection; as such the quality control of the modified version is the responsibility of the user. It uses standard laboratory equipment including plate reader and incubators. A plate washer is also required because of the sensitivity of the assay. Training was provided by the assay developer and this was very helpful in optimizing assay performance and minimizing variability. The assay setup included a dilution that is done in tubes or the plate. This evaluation was done using tubes so that a larger sample volume could be used to improve pipetting reproducibility and minimize variability. The diluted samples could be transferred to the plate using multichannel pipettors to minimize pipetting errors. Using titer tubes for dilutions also allowed for faster plate set-up to minimize time spent at RT before the first incubation step at 4°C.

The assay developers provided controls and created data templates to use in recording the assay and analysing data. The reliability of accompanying documents e.g. spreadsheets, data files, QC charts, is vital to the performance of the assay. The operator must be vigilant in transferring data and maintaining these documents to ensure information is correct. It is important that if this assay is adopted by other users that they ensure appropriate controls are available and properly validated. Furthermore, the user should consider appropriate document control of any data sheets used to support assay validation or data analysis.

This determination of recent and longstanding

The result reflects the signal intensity for the high-avidity HIV-1 antibodies; longstanding infection will have higher avidity antibodies to the HIV antigens whereas recently infected individuals will have lower avidity antibodies. The Avidity index (AI) is the measure of the higher avidity antibodies over the total HIV-antibody response.

Advantages

The assay takes approximately 4 hours from start to finish and could be performed by any technician who is familiar with EIA methods. It is feasible to perform 2 runs per day, 2 plates at a time screening a total of 168 samples/day. This assay could be easily transferred to domestic or international research laboratories and requires no specialized equipment besides that of which is found in general clinical and research laboratories. The assay controls showed variability in OD values and AI values from plate run to plate run; the results, however, generally maintained the clinical determination of recent or longstanding infection.

Target Product Profile performance

Specification	Acceptable Performance	Ideal Performance	How does Bio-Rad Avidity fit?
Intended Use	Population-based incidence estimate	Population-based incidence estimate, prevention-trial planning, community-level prevention intervention studies	It has a long recency period, it has a sub-optimal false recent rate. Included in a RITA, this FRR could be reduced.
Target Population	Specific to clade	All clades	Performance of non-clade B is worse than clade B. Not appropriate for international population based incidence surveillance.
False Recent Rate (FRR)	Confidently measured to be less than 2% in different populations (with different clades, epidemic phases, treatment coverage etc)	0% in all population (No evidence of false-recent classifications).	Failed - 6%
Mean Duration	4 months (95% CI, +/- 0.2)	1 year (95% CI, +/- 0.2)	Acceptable - 333 days (95% CI: 302-363),
Algorithm	Included in a RITA	None required	CEPHIA recommends use of this assay to be included in a RITA
Analyte	Any	Any	Anti- p160, gp36 and anti-p24

Sample Type	Frozen serum, frozen plasma	Frozen serum or plasma , dried blood spots (or other easily obtained and stored sample)	Acceptable -Frozen serum or plasma.
Sample Volume	1 mL	10 uL or fingerstick	Acceptable -20ul for initial dilution.
Infrastructure requirements	Centralized laboratory facility (clean water and electricity available)	None (all reagents and necessary materials to run assay are in self-contained kit)	Centralized Lab.
Storage/Shipping Conditions	4-25 °C	Ambient temperature	2-8°C
Incubation Temperature	4-25 °C	Ambient temperature	37°C and 24°C Incubator
Shelf Life	9 months	>18 months	Acceptable -9 months
Training	Laboratory technician can be proficient with one week's training based on proficiency testing	Minimal training would allow any health worker to conduct the assay	Acceptable - Laboratory technician can be proficient with one week's training based on proficiency testing
Regulatory Pathway	GMP or ISO 13485 or equivalent, and/or approval by national governing body	FDA and equivalents	The clinical diagnostic system is FDA approved; the modified version of the assay has not been approved for diagnostic use.

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Appendix

1. Evaluation Protocol

Background

The Bio-Rad Avidity Assay is to be evaluated by the CEPHIA group as part of The Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation funded project, 'Development of specimen repository and evaluation of assays for identification of recent HIV infection and estimation of HIV incidence'. The group will also undertake evaluations of a number of other available assays for HIV recency. Each of these evaluations will have their own CEPHIA Book Report available.

Evaluation Purpose

To advance the understanding of currently available assays that can identify recent HIV infection; to better describe the duration of the infection state in which they identify recent infection; and to determine the rate at which they misclassify specimens as from recent infections

Conduct of the evaluation

All CEPHIA evaluations are conducted following the **CEPHIA Quality Management Strategy** (Document 002) which details the quality planning, quality control and quality assurance in place at Public Health England (PHE), Microbiology Services (MS), Colindale and the collaborating organisations of Blood Systems Research Institute (BSRI), San Francisco, University of California, San Francisco (UCSF) and South African Centre for Epidemiological Modelling and Analysis (SACEMA), University of Stellenbosch, South Africa, to ensure the delivery of the Bill & Melinda Gates Funded (BMGF) Project.

The main objectives of the quality strategy are: to define the quality requirements, how they are to be met, who is responsible for meeting requirements, and helping to align quality strategies between the multiple sites involved in the overall project.

The CEPHIA Quality Management Strategy details the quality procedures in place for all CEPHIA evaluations with regards to Project Organisation – roles, responsibilities and personnel, Facilities, Equipment, Standard Operating procedures (SOP), Worksheets, Plans, Sub-contracting, Conduct of project, Computer systems, Safety and risk, Method validations, Results

, Reporting process and templates, Repeat analysis, Retention of data/specimens, Confidentiality. The quality strategy will be based on UK CPA standards and also MHRA Good Clinical Practise 'Guidance on the maintenance of regulatory compliance in laboratories that perform the analysis or evaluation of clinical trial samples', it will also refer to local site regulations and standards.

- **The assay under evaluation will be tested in exactly the manner documented in the manufacturers/developers separate instructions.**
- **Evaluator(s) will strictly adhere to the quality requirements laid out in the CEPHIA Quality Management Strategy.**
- **Prior to beginning the evaluation, the manufacturer/developer will be invited, if they so wish, to provide training to the evaluator in the use of the assay kit and equipment and to satisfy themselves that the evaluator(s) is trained sufficiently.**

Specimen Handling

A main objective of this project is to compile large-volume, standardized sample sets appropriate for comparative evaluation of tests for recent HIV infection in an accessible central repository.

These serum samples will be sourced by the CEPHIA team at University of California San Francisco (UCSF), blinded so evaluator(s) will not know the expected results, then aliquotted at the central repository (Blood Systems Research Institute, San Francisco) and shipped to the relevant test site.

Documentation

The CEPHIA group have compiled a folder of documents relating to the plans, procedures and protocols required for the high quality performance and completion of the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation funded project. These documents are securely stored in a management-only access folder until the project end. Some relevant documents are available for public reading on the CEPHIA website at <http://www.incidence-estimation.com/archivesuploads/index/NAME/11>

Other aspects of the evaluation

Technical appraisal of the procedure, assay kit and equipment required for the performance of the assay. This may include ease of use, reliability, packaging, clarity, health and safety considerations.

Discordant results

A discrepancy may arise at the test site and should be investigated by an appropriately trained person prior to data being verified and reported for analysis. If a discrepancy is identified at the analysis site (SACEMA), a report detailing the error will be sent to the test site for further investigation.

Analysis of results and evaluation report

The raw laboratory data is compiled and verified at the test site. It is stored electronically in a Data Table formatted as described in the *CEPHIA Data Processing Protocol: Data Flow, Recording and Standard Formats*.

Verified and formatted data is e-mailed to the analysis site (SACEMA). The analysis site will run data through checks and generate a report prior to using the data for analysis. Data analysis will be reported in the CEPHIA Book. The manufacturer/developer of the assay concerned will be given the opportunity to comment on results prior to any publishing of data.

2. CEPHIA Project Management Contact Details

1. PHE – Public Health England, Microbiology Services, Colindale, London, UK
2. BSRI - Blood Systems Research Institute, San Francisco
3. UCSF – University of California, San Francisco
4. SACEMA - South African Centre for Epidemiological Modelling and Analysis

Project Management Team:				
Gary Murphy	PHE	London, UK	Assay evaluation	gary.murphy@phe.gov.uk
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Contact details for manufacturer

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Manufacturer's comments.

A draft copy of this report was provided to the assay manufacturer and we are grateful for their input. This highlighted a small number of factual errors that have been corrected in this version. In addition they made a number of suggestions which we have considered in preparing the final report. Furthermore, the following comments were received from the manufacturer:

Having reviewed the draft report we generally agree with the recommendations and conclusions made by the CEPHIA group of this very important study of the CDC developer's avidity modification of the FDA approved and licensed Bio-Rad GS HIV-1/HIV-2 *PLUS O* EIA assay kit. We also feel that this very important validated sample set could have been used to evaluate more than a single cutoff value for HIV avidity especially with the relatively long MDRI period found (Christopher Bentsen).

Developer's comments.

A draft copy of this report was provided to the developer of the modified version of the assay and we are grateful for their input. This highlighted a small number of factual errors that have been corrected in this version. In addition they made a number of suggestions which we have considered in preparing the final report. Furthermore, the following comments were received from the developer:

As the developer of the assay we generally agree with conclusions presented within this evaluation and appreciate the value of the independent evaluation. The assay was primarily developed for US domestic use and the performance described in this evaluation represents similar findings of the CDC with subtype B specimens. One additional caveat related to the analysis is that CDC will be recommending an AI cutoff of 30% as the cutoff for recent infection instead of the 40% described in this analysis. The cutoff was optimized after the initiation of the CEPHIA evaluation and per the SOP for evaluation CEPHIA completed their analysis based on the parameters submitted at the initiation of an evaluation.

Enquiries

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